

Journal home page:
<http://www.iajpr.com/index.php/en/>

INDO AMERICAN
JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL
RESEARCH

Formulation and Evaluation of Gastroretentive Floating Microballoons of Norfloxacin

Joydeep Dutta^{*1}, G.Ganesh Kumar², Vikas Dash³, Savendu Saha⁴

^{*}Vignan Institute of Pharmaceuticals Sciences, Vignan Hills, Pochampalli.(A.P.)

²Srikrupa Institute of Pharmaceuticals Sciences, Siddipet, (A.P.)

³Kanak Manjari Institute of Pharmaceuticals Sciences, Atchend, Rourkela, Orrisa.

⁴Prasad Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Warangal, A.P.

ARTICLE INFO

Received 22 July 2011
Received in revised form 21
August 2011
Accepted 25 September 2011
Available online October 2011

Keywords

Eudragit RS 100,
floating microballoons,
Eudragit RL 100,
In vitro release,
Norfloxacin.

ABSTRACT

The present study involves preparation and evaluation of floating microballoons with norfloxacin as model drug for prolongation of gastric residence time. The microballoons were prepared by the solvent evaporation method using a combination of polymer Eudragit RS 100 and Eudragit L 100. The shape and surface morphology of prepared microballoons were characterized by optical and scanning electron microscopy, respectively. *In vitro* drug release studies were performed and drug release kinetics was evaluated using the linear regression method. Effects of stirring rate during preparation, polymer concentration, solvent composition and dissolution medium on the size of microballoons, and drug release were also observed. The prepared microballoons exhibited prolonged drug release (8 hours) and remained buoyant for >10 hours. The mean particle size increased and the drug release rate decreased at higher polymer concentration. No significant effect of the stirring rate during preparation on drug release was observed. *In vitro* studies demonstrated diffusion-controlled drug release from the microballoons.

Corresponding author

Joydeep Dutta

Vignan Institute of Pharmaceuticals Sciences, Vignan Hills, Pochampalli.(A.P.)

Mobile: 9966613613, Email id: ganesh_pharmaco007@yahoo.co.in

Please cite this article in press as Joydeep Dutta et al., Formulation and Evaluation of Gastroretentive Floating Microballoons of Norfloxacin. Indo American Journal of Pharm Research. 2011;1(5):415-426.

INTRODUCTION

Floating drug delivery systems or hydrodynamically balanced systems are among the several approaches that have been developed in order to increase the gastric residence time of dosage forms. Both single and multiple unit systems have been developed. The single-unit floating systems are more popular but have a disadvantage owing to their "all-or-nothing" emptying process leading to high variability of the gastrointestinal transit time. Still, the multiple-unit dosage forms may be better suited because they are claimed to reduce the inter subject variability in absorption and lower the probability of dose dumping. Such a dosage form can be distributed widely throughout the gastrointestinal tract (GIT), affording the possibility of a longer lasting and more reliable release of the drug from the dosage form¹.

Both natural and synthetic polymers have been used to prepare floating microballoons. Kawashima *et al.* prepared hollow microballoons or microballoons of ibuprofen by the emulsion-solvent diffusion method using acrylic polymers. The microballoons exhibited good *in vitro* floatability and drug release decreased drastically with increasing polymer concentration. Floating microballoons of cellulose acetate loaded with four different drugs were prepared using the solvent diffusion-evaporation method. The microballoons remained buoyant for more than 12 hours. Methylcellulose and chitosan micropellets loaded with lansoprazole had a lower density than gastric contents and exhibited better encapsulation efficiencies. Other polymer solution systems that have been used to prepare floating microballoons are polycarbonate/dichloromethane, cellulose acetate butyrate/Eudragit RL100 mixture in acetone, and Eudragit S100/*i*-propanol³.

Norfloxacin is a potent anti bacterial agent having very broad spectrum of its activity. It is more soluble in acidic pH and slightly soluble at neutral or alkaline pH conditions (intestinal environment). It acts by inhibiting DNA Gyrase and hence it is

specific bacterial DNA Gyrase blocker, thus it inhibits the synthesis of DNA in bacteria leading to its rapid lyses. But fortunately it does not act on mammalian cell hence mammalian DNA Gyrase remain unaffected leading to its potent and specific anti bacterial activity.

It is poorly absorbed from the lower GIT and has a short elimination half life (5-6 hours). The objective of the present study was to develop floating microballoons of metformin in order to achieve an extended retention in the upper GIT, which may result in enhanced absorption and there by improved bioavailability. The prepared microballoons were evaluated for size, *in vitro* metformin release, buoyancy, and incorporation efficiency (IE). The effect of various formulation variables on the size and drug release was investigated⁴.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Norfloxacin was obtained as a gift sample from Sun Pharma Healthcare, India. Sodium chloride was obtained from S.D. Fine Chemicals Ltd., India. Dichloromethane, Eudragit, and Tween 80, isopropanol were obtained from Central Drug House (P) Ltd., India. All other chemicals/reagents used were of analytical grade. Microballoons with an internal hollow structure were prepared by solvent diffusion-evaporation method. Equal quantities of two polymers i.e. Eudragit L-100 and Eudragit RS-100 (400 mg each) were dissolved in 8 ml ethanol, followed by the addition of 2 ml isopropanol and 5 ml dichloromethane. Then 400 mg of drug (norfloxacin) was homogeneously dispersed in this polymer solution.

This polymer solution was slowly introduced into 200 ml of poly-vinyl alcohol (PVA) aqueous solution with stirring at 300 rpm using a mechanical stirrer equipped with a 3 blade propeller. The solution was stirred for 1 hour and microballoons were collected by filtration and washed 3 times with distilled water, dried at 40°C and kept in desiccators.

Table 1: Formulation of Gastroretentive Floating Microballoons of Norfloxacin

S. No	Formulation Code	Drug :Polymer Ratio	Solvent Ratio {D: E: I}	Emulsifier Conc.	Temp.	Stirring Rate
1.	O ₁ ESTDP	1:2	5:8:2	0.75	30	300
2.	O ₂ ESTDP	1:2	5:6:4	0.75	30	300
3.	O ₃ ESTDP	1:2	5:4:2	0.75	30	300
4.	O ₄ ESTDP	1:2	5:2:8	0.75	30	300
5.	OESTD ₁ P	1:2	5:8:2	0.75	30	300
6.	OESTD ₂ P	1:3	5:8:2	0.75	30	300
7.	OESTD ₃ P	1:4	5:8:2	0.75	30	300
8.	OESTD ₄ P	1:5	5:8:2	0.75	30	300
9.	OE ₁ STDP	1:2	5:8:2	0.50	30	300
10.	OE ₂ STDP	1:2	5:8:2	0.75	30	300
11.	OE3STDP	1:2	5:8:2	1.0	30	300
12.	OE4STDP	1:2	5:8:2	1.25	30	300
13.	OEST1DP	1:2	5:8:2	0.75	10	300
14.	OEST2DP	1:2	5:8:2	0.75	20	300
15.	OEST3DP	1:2	5:8:2	0.75	30	300
16.	OEST4DP	1:2	5:8:2	0.75	40	300
17.	OES1TDP	1:2	5:8:2	0.75	30	200
18.	OES2TDP	1:2	5:8:2	0.75	30	300
19.	OES3TDP	1:2	5:8:2	0.75	30	300
20.	OES4TDP	1:2	5:8:2	0.75	30	500

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characterization of norfloxacin microballoons

Size distribution and morphology

The floating microspheres were examined by **optical** and **scanning electron microscopy (SEM)**. A freshly prepared suspension of microballoons in 0.1% tween 20 was examined on an optical microscope.

The size of the microspheres was measured using a photo microscope. Around 100 particles from each formulation were measured and the observed data of each formulation are presented in Table 1. The photomicrographs of different formulations were taken which are shown in Fig 5 and Fig 6.

The surface morphology of microballoons selected on the basis of optical microscopy was visualized by scanning electron microscopy. The samples for SEM were prepared by lightly sprinkling the microballoons powder on a double adhesive tape which stuck to an aluminium stub.

The stubs were then coated with gold to a thickness of about 300°A using a sputter coater. These samples were than randomly scanned and photomicrographs were taken.

Percent yield of microballoons

The prepared microballoons were collected and weighed. The weight of microballoons was divided by the total weight of all the non-volatile components used for the preparation of the microballoons.

$$\% \text{ yield} = \frac{\text{weight of microballoons collected}}{\text{wt. of all non-volatile components used for the preparation}} \times 100$$

i. Effect of solvent ratio:

In this study, the organic solvent for the polymer was varied. Different combination of solvents i.e. dichloromethane : ethanol : isopropanol (D:E:I) were taken to see their effect on particle size and percent yield of microspheres which are reported in Table 2 and shown in Fig. 1.

Table 2: Effect of solvent ratio on particle size and % yield of microballoons

[

S.NO.	FORMULATION CODE	SOLVENT RATIO	% YIELD
1.	O ₁ ESTDP	5:8:2	90.1
2.	O ₂ ESTDP	5:6:4	86.4
3.	O ₃ ESTDP	5:4:6	81.3
4.	O ₄ ESTDP	5:2:8	77.7

Fig. 1: % yield of microballoons at different solvent ratio (D:E:I)

ii. Effect of drug: polymer ratio:

For the study the drug amount was kept constant and polymer amount was varied to give different drug: polymer ratios. The effect was seen on size distribution and percent yield of microspheres. All other parameters were kept constant for the study. The results are prepared in Table 4 and graphically shown in Fig. 3.

Loading efficiency

The amount of drug associated with the microballoons was analyzed in terms of the percent entrapped drug.

Percent entrapped drug

The prepared microballoons were digested in minimum quantity of ethanol (95%), and then diluted with acetate buffer (pH 4.6) up to 10 ml. The digested homogenate was centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 3 minutes and the supernatant after suitable dilution was assayed for norfloxacin spectrophotometrically. The drug entrapment values with different variables are shown in Table 3.7- 3.11 and graphically shown in Fig. 3.10-3.14. The percentage drug entrapment is calculated from the equation given below.

Table 3: Effect of drug: polymer ratio on % yield of microballoons

S.NO	FORMULATION CODE	DRUG:POLYMER RATIO	% YIELD
1.	OESTD ₁ P	1:2	89.9
2.	OESTD ₂ P	1:3	82.7
3.	OESTD ₃ P	1:4	76.4
4.	OESTD ₄ P	1:5	72.0

Fig. 2: % yield of microballoons at different drug: polymer ratio.

% Drug entrapped = Amount of drug in the microballoons (actual content)/ Amount of drug used in formulation (theoretical content) x 100

Table 6: Effect of polymer: polymer ratio (Eudragit L 100: Eudrag 100)

S.No.	Formulation Code	Eudragit L 100: Eudragit RS 100	Diameter (μ)	Frequency (n)	n×d	Particle size	% yield
1	OESTDP ₁	1:0	22.5	3	67.5	41.8	90.1
			30.0	7	210		
			37.5	41	1537.5		
			45.0	32	1440		
			52.5	17	892.5		
2	OESTDP ₂	0:1	22.5	2	45	41.18	88.2
			30.0	19	570		
			37.5	19	712.5		
			45.0	48	2160		
			52.5	12	630		
3	OESTDP ₃	1:2	22.5	2	45	42.00	89.2
			30.0	15	450		
			37.5	25	937.5		
			45.0	37	1665		
			52.5	21	1102.5		
4	OESTDP ₄	1:3	22.5	3	67.5	41.33	86.3
			30.0	17	510		
			37.5	21	787.5		
			45.0	44	1980		
			52.5	15	787.5		
5	OESTDP ₅	2:3	22.5	3	67.5	40.88	87.7
			30.0	15	450		
			37.5	28	1050		
			45.0	42	1890		
			52.5	12	630		
6	OESTDP ₆	3:2	22.5	2	45	40.88	89.6
			30.0	7	210		
			37.5	41	1537.5		
			45.0	44	1980		
			52.5	6	315		
7	OESTDP ₇	3:1	22.5	3	67.5	42.68	90.0
			30.0	21	630		
			37.5	35	1312.5		
			45.0	28	1260		
			52.5	19	997.5		
8	OESTDP ₈	2:1	22.5	2	45	40.35	89.8
			30.0	25	750		
			37.5	21	787.5		
			45.0	37	1665		
			52.5	15	787.5		

Fig. 7: % yield of microspheres at different polymer: polymer ratio (Eudragit L100: Eudragit RS 100)

Table 7: Drug entrapment values at different polymer ratio (EudragitL 100: Eudragit RS100)

S. No.	Formulation Code	Eudragit L 100 : Eudragit RS 100	% entrapped drug
1	OESTDP ₁	1:0	77.9
2	OESTDP ₂	0:1	71.8
3	OESTDP ₃	1:2	73.8
4	OESTDP ₄	1:3	73.2
5	OESTDP ₅	2:3	74.4
6	OESTDP ₆	3:2	75.2
7	OESTDP ₇	3:1	77.4
8	OESTDP ₈	2:1	75.2

Fig. 8: % drug entrapment at different polymer: polymer ratio (Eudragit L100 :Eudragit RS100)

In vitro floating test

The floating test of the microballoons was carried out using the Dissolution test Apparatus method II specified in the USP XX. The unloaded microballoons (800 mg) were spread over the

surface of the simulated gastric fluid pH 1.2 (900 ml, 37 ± 0.5°C) which was agitated by a paddle rotated at 100 rpm. Dissolution test solution SGF (pH 1.2) containing Tween 20 (0.02% w/v) was

used as dispersion medium to simulate gastric fluid. After agitation for a previously determined interval, the microballoons that were floating and the ones that settled to the bottom of the flask were recovered separately. After drying, the fraction of the microballoons was weighed; the %

buoyancy of the microballoons was calculated by the following equation:

$$\text{Percent buoyancy} = \frac{Q_f}{(Q_f + Q_s)} \times 100$$

Where, Q_s is the weight of the settled microballoons, Q_f is weight of microballoons that were floating.

Table 8: Percent buoyancy of different unloaded microballoons formulations in SGF (pH 1.2) at 37 ± 0.5°C

S.No.	Formulation Code	% Buoyancy at different time intervals (hour)							
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	24
1	OESTD ₁ P	95.2	91.8	90.6	85.8	80.3	78.6	72.0	56.2
2	OESTDP ₁	97.1	92.8	88.0	83.6	80.1	79.8	76.7	60.9
3	OESTDP ₂	92.1	89.2	85.3	83.8	78.2	74.1	69.8	51.8
4	OESTDP ₃	95.4	92.7	88.7	84.7	79.9	77.1	71.3	54.1
5	OESTDP ₄	95.0	90.3	88.2	84.3	79.6	75.2	70.0	52.6
6	OESTDP ₅	95.6	91.7	90.2	84.9	80.1	78.2	71.9	54.8
7	OESTDP ₆	96.0	91.7	89.8	84.7	80.9	79.3	72.8	58.7
8	OESTDP ₇	93.6	92.7	90.2	86.2	82.1	79.7	76.3	60.1
9	OESTDP ₈	96.2	92.3	89.3	84.4	81.3	79.2	75.1	59.4

Fig. 9: % buoyancy of different unloaded formulations in SGF at 37 ± 1°C

In vitro drug release

The optimized nine formulations of norfloxacin microspheres e.g. OESTD₁P, OESTDP₁.....OESTDP₈ were selected for the in vitro drug release studies. The drug release studies

of microballoons were carried out in Dissolution Test Apparatus II USP XX by the paddle method. Microballoons equivalent to 800 mg of norfloxacin were gently spread over the surface of 900 ml of dissolution medium (SGF pH 1.2,

Acetate buffer pH 4.6, Mixed Phosphate buffer pH 6.8 and SIF pH 7.4) as specified in the Indian pharmacopoeia 1985.

The paddle was rotated at 100 rpm and the temperature of dissolution medium was thermostatically controlled at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. The samples were withdrawn at a suitable intervals of time from the dissolution vessel and were assayed after appropriate dilution spectrophotometrically at 278 nm in acidic medium and 273 nm in

alkaline medium for norfloxacin using **Shimadzu 1700 (UV-Visible spectrophotometer)**

The effect of different polymer ratios on the release from floating microballoons was seen in four different dissolution mediums viz. SGF (pH 1.2), Acetate buffer pH 4.6, Mixed phosphate buffer pH 6.8, and SGF (pH 7.4) which are shown in Table 9 and shown graphically in Fig. 10. The drug release of each formulation was compared in four different mediums.

Table 9: *In vitro* drug release profile of norfloxacin from optimized microballoons in SGF (pH 1.2) at λ_{max} 278 nm.

Sl. No.	Formulation Code	% cumulative drug release (hour)							
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	24
1	OESTD ₁ P	7.2	14.0	20.3	26.6	32.2	37.2	41.3	89.6
2	OESTDP ₁	6.1	8.2	9.8	10.3	11.1	11.6	12.2	21.3
3	OESTDP ₂	11.6	25.9	37.8	46.2	54.3	61.3	64.4	93.2
4	OESTDP ₃	7.6	16.9	25.7	36.8	43.9	51.4	54.8	91.3
5	OESTDP ₄	8.0	20.2	32.9	41.3	48.7	56.2	60.1	92.3
6	OESTDP ₅	7.4	15.8	23.2	30.1	37.3	42.6	46.4	90.3
7	OESTDP ₆	6.8	13.6	18.4	23.1	29.0	32.1	36.2	76.9
8	OESTDP ₇	6.6	11.8	14.9	20.1	22.8	26.0	29.7	56.2
9	OESTDP ₈	6.7	12.3	15.2	20.8	24.7	28.6	31.5	65.9

Fig. 10: *In vitro* drug release profile of norfloxacin from optimized microballoons in SGF (pH 1.2) at λ_{max} 278 nm.

Table 10: In vitro drug release profile of norfloxacin from optimized microballoons in Acetate buffer (pH 4.6) at λ_{max} 278 nm

S.No.	Formulation Code	% cumulative drug release (hours)							
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	24
1	OESTD ₁ P	6.9	15.1	21.3	25.8	31	36.3	40.7	86.3
2	OESTDP ₁	6	8.1	9.6	10.0	10.8	11.1	11.9	19.9
3	OESTDP ₂	11.1	24.9	37.6	45.8	54.2	61.7	65.6	93.1
4	OESTDP ₃	7.4	15.6	24.1	35.2	43.2	47.9	51.2	91.2
5	OESTDP ₄	9.6	18.4	30.7	39.8	47.6	55.3	58.9	92.1
6	OESTDP ₅	7.3	15.6	21.9	30.12	35.2	39.9	44.1	89.8
7	OESTDP ₆	6.6	12.7	17.3	24.2	28.1	31.1	34.3	72.5
8	OESTDP ₇	6.4	11.9	14.8	19.6	21.7	24.8	27.5	51.8
9	OESTDP ₈	6.4	11.8	14.7	19.9	23.6	27.4	30.1	61.7

Fig. 11: In vitro drug release profile of norfloxacin from optimized microballoons in acetate buffer (pH 4.6) at λ_{max} 278 nm.

Fig 12: SEM of Norfloxacin microballoons.

CONCLUSION

An optimized oral controlled drug delivery system for norfloxacin was developed via floating microballoons prepared using a combination of polymers (Eudragit L 100 and Eudragit RS 100) to regulate the drug release in the upper part of gastrointestinal tract. The *In-vitro* dissolution studies carried out with the floating microballoons of norfloxacin prepared by solvent diffusion evaporation method suggests that microballoons may deliver the drug at the site of its maximum absorption, thereby increasing the bioavailability as well as reduce the gastrointestinal side effects of the drug.

REFERENCES

1. Arora S, Ali J, Ahuja A, Khar RK, Baboota S. 2005. Floating drug delivery system: A Review, *AAPS Pharm.sci.Tech*, 6(3): E372-E390.
2. Robinson JR, Lee Vincent HL, *Controlled Drug Delivery-Fundamentals and Applications*, 2nd edition, Marcel Dekker Inc., New York, pp 555-580.
3. Chien YW, *Novel Drug Delivery Systems*, 2nd edition, Marcel Dekker, Inc. New York, pp 1-42.
4. Wise DL, *Handbook of Pharmaceutical Controlled Release Technology*, Marcel Dekker Inc., New York, pp 329-344.
5. Rathbone JM, Hadgraft J, Michael SR, 2003, *Modified Release Drug Delivery Technology*, pp 1-11.
6. Sato Y, Kawashima Y, Takeuchi H, Yamamoto H. 2004. In-vitro and in-vivo evaluation of riboflavin containing micro balloons for a floating controlled drug delivery system in healthy humans, *International journal of pharmaceutics*, 275: 97-107.
7. Sato Y, Kawashima Y, Takeuchi H, Yamamoto H. 2004. In-vitro evaluation of floating and drug releasing behaviors of hollow microspheres (microballoons) prepared by the emulsion solvent diffusion method, *European journal of pharmaceutics and biopharmaceutics*, 57:235- 243.
8. Sato Y, Kawashima Y, Takeuchi H, Yamamoto H. 2003. Physicochemical properties to determine the buoyancy of hollow micro sphere (microballons) prepared by the emulsion solvent diffusion method, *European journal of pharmaceutics and biopharmaceutics*.55: 297-304.
9. Kawashima Y, Niwa T, Takeuchi H, Hino T, Itoh Y. 1991. Preparation of multiple unit hollow microspheres with acrylic resin containing tranilast and their drug release characteristic (in vitro) and floating behavior (in vitro), *International journal of controlled release*, 16:279-290.
10. Jain SK, Agrawal GP, Jain NK. 2006. A novel calcium silicate based microspheres of repaglinide: In vivo investigation, *Journal of controlled release*, 113:111-116

20110030201196202